

INTEGRATED ANALYSIS OF EDUCATIONAL POEMS IN MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LESSONS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract: *In the article, an integrated analysis of educational poems in mother tongue and reading classes in primary grades. The analysis and research of educational poems, which form a special category in Uzbek children's poetry, and the moral and educational importance of studying them in primary classes are discussed.*

Key words: *integration, moral, spiritual, didactic, independent, artistic, imagery, pedagogical, theoretical, thinking.*

The subject of reading consisted mainly of artistic style texts conveying abstract concepts. The texts and poems selected for the new textbook are artistic, informative, and scientific-popular texts that help the child to enter social life. In the current textbooks, there are no tasks for developing listening comprehension competence, but in the new one, separate tasks for each subject have been developed to develop this competence. Tasks allocated for the development of reading comprehension competence were mainly focused on the information openly expressed in the text or didactic elements. Now the textbook will have questions and assignments covering all parts of the reading comprehension competency. Until now, the purpose of teaching the mother tongue was to teach the grammar of the language, to memorize the rules related to the structure of the language. Only the most important rules are left in the new textbook. More emphasis is placed on colorful images and interesting tasks. Importantly, now there is a "Teacher's Book" for teachers, and an "Exercise Book" for students. Old textbooks focus on teaching language structure. New textbooks emphasize lexicological and semantic aspects of the language rather than the structure of the language. That is, the main attention is

focused on aspects such as the word, its meanings, substitutes, places of use, vocabulary.

Texts taken from current textbooks emphasize didactic importance rather than appropriateness for the child's age. The presented didactics are based on age-appropriate texts and poems on interesting topics. Together with the writers, the texts were reworked. Words in the textbooks that might be unclear were left unexplained. In new textbooks, words that are difficult for a child to understand are placed in a special dictionary at the back of the textbook. In addition, special exercises have been developed on them. Art, visual and optional essays and dictations can be used when studying subjects of the second, third and fourth grades, not forgetting that the development of speech is considered the main thing in the mother tongue classes. When choosing an essay and a dictation, it is necessary to choose topics that are characteristic of nature and that will cultivate children's love for nature. Essays and dictations educate children to love nature, teach them to respect it, help them understand the moral, aesthetic and ecological responsibilities and duties of nature.

In their stories, children gradually learn to insert wise words, opinions of scholars, use proverbs and phrases in their place, draw pictures in essays and dictations. The purpose of this is to learn more deeply about nature, to feel it, to teach to be attentive to the environment. At the same time, in native language and reading literacy classes, they are taught to create a story or a fairy tale based on a picture, to name them, to make plans, to put the parts correctly. This helps students to assess the situation correctly.

The presence of interdisciplinary common topics aims to combine these methods and provide students with a wider range of knowledge, skills and abilities. If two subjects are combined, the lesson should be planned in such a way that the information obtained from other subjects is complementary to each other, and that information is deepened, well assimilated and well stored in the student's memory. Only then can this embodied lesson differ from other lessons and show its effectiveness. In conclusion, the more effectively we use interdisciplinary integration in primary classes, the higher the level of students' knowledge will be.

The more rapidly they develop, the more they connect disciplines, differentiate them, and combine theory and practice.

Children of the 21st century have a broad and sharp outlook and thinking. In the years of independence, paying attention to artistically high examples of children's literature, forming moral-educational, socio-political education in students through the analysis of works that reflect the interests of children of the new century, their mental and spiritual world, and their attitude to social life. is given importance. The creations of Dilshod Rajabni, one of the representatives of Uzbek children's poetry of the period of independence, have a great role in the formation of the spiritual world of students. Dilshod Rajab is one of the talented representatives of Uzbek children's poetry. He was born in 1964 in Shafirkon district of Bukhara region in an intellectual family. In 1994-2004, he worked in various positions at the State Press Committee of Uzbekistan, at the publishing house of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan "Literary Fund", and at the Republican "Memorial of Martyrs" charity fund. Since 2005, he has been working as a chief editor in the joint editorial office of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Muhofaza+" magazine and "Vaziyat" newspaper. More than a hundred scientific, scientific-popular and publicist articles have been published. Winner of the international competition for the 6th "Golden Pen" National Award in the field of journalism (2011). Poet, candidate of philological sciences Dilshod Rajab contributes to the development of Uzbek children's literature with a number of children's books, scientific and popular scientific articles.

At the same time, he works as a member of the Children's and Adolescent Literature Council of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan.

Some of his poems are being published in the textbook of mother tongue and reading literacy. For example, in part 2, the poem "Let not the writing be "Evil"" is given.

If you write "F" for "Q",

"Elephant" will appear.

When "Gado" ends,

Of course, it will be perfect.
Don't call "Nightingale" "Gulgul"
Do not replace "B" with "G".
Do not write "R" instead of "Z",
Don't let the "eye" become "blind".
Substituting "S" for "L"
Don't make a clear "stream" "Mud".
Jumble the letters
Don't ramble on.

In the above poem, the main idea is to use words correctly. It is intended to teach children to use words correctly and to use them in their place from a young age. We can certainly find educational poems in the works of all poets.

When we teach the above poem to the students, it will be easy to get the answers to the following questions: Who is the author of the poem?

1. What other poems of the author are you familiar with?
2. Why did the poet compare the words "do" and "elephant".
3. Do you know the meaning of the words "Gado" and "Ado"?
4. Explain the phrase "Don't make a clear stream 'Mud'".
5. What can actually happen?

This poem of the poet first of all teaches to speak correctly, but in another way, it helps to increase the vocabulary of students and also helps in the process of working with dictionaries.

These questions will help the students to understand the meaning of the poem better and more consciously. This poem will help students to develop proper reading and writing skills. From the title of this poem by Dilshad Rajab, he urges the readers to enlightenment. . We will be able to enter the poem by explaining the spelling of the word "evil" and how its meaning changes by changing the number of letters. The writing explains to the reader why he is evil in his own language in a simple and wonderful way.

If this poem is explained to the student in a visual way, it will be more understandable to the student, that is, it will help the student to form his imagination by seeing the poem he is reading through his eyes.

In general, educational poems in children's poetry help elementary school students to strengthen their knowledge acquired at school, to discover new aspects through their artistic interpretation. In this sense, the importance of educational poems, which can provide artistic-aesthetic pleasure and spiritual nourishment, is still relevant and significant in memorizing the correct rules, completing theoretical assignments, and spending moments of relaxation for bored students.

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